

WORLD EDUCATION CONNECT

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842

ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

MULTIDISCIPLINARY E-PUBLICATION

Vol. IV Issue IV, April 2024

Monthly Issue

International Circulation

Pinagpala
PUBLISHING SERVICES

NBDB Reg. No. 3269

DTI Business Reg. No. 3034433

TIN 293-150-678 / Business Permit No. 8183

San Vicente, Tarlac City, Philippines, 2300

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PROJECT UP (UGNAYANG PAGBASA): AN APPROACH TO IMPROVE READING COMPREHENSION IN ARLING PANLIPUNAN 7 OF WAWA NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL

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This action research aims to enhance the reading comprehension of grade 7 learners to achieve their academic performance — through the help of stakeholders. Reading comprehension is the accurate measure of reading literacy. Comprehension is considered as the essence of reading as it accounts for the process that supports the effective extraction of meaning from a written passage (Alghonaim, 2020). As claimed by Helarde (2021), reading is the mother of all study skills. Furthermore, Tomas et al (2021), states that reading provides readers with a new set of learnings and a vast array of knowledge that will benefit their academic journey. The researchers encourage to create innovations, approaches, and teaching strategies to enhance the reading comprehension since students learning and academic achievements will always be a heart of teaching.

The researchers are aware that one of the factors that affect the level of performance of the learner in Araling Panlipunan is the poor reading comprehension level of the learners — this urged the researchers to innovate an approach to address the needs of the learners. Based on the LOA results, during the first quarter of school year 2021-2022, AP 7 has a 30.73 mean and 51.22 MPS, which is the lowest in AP in all grade level. Hence, the researchers will use grade 7 learners as respondents of this study.

With the aforementioned scenario, the researchers came up with the idea to pursue Project UP (Ugnayang Pagbasa) as an approach that will need a peer and stakeholders, like alumni, barangay day care teachers, volunteers, SSG officers, and other organizations who are willing to assist in this program. They will be asked to give their assistance by sharing expertise, knowledge, and time to render service in a reading intervention plan. In this unique way, Project UP (Ugnayang Pagbasa) will be a leeway and a bridge to connect (Ugnay) the stakeholders to the learners and the community. Based on the study of Nicdao and Anjo (2019), the stakeholders have a hand and a great stake in providing assistance to the education of the young learners as they are the agents in the community with the most suitable and adequate resources, and this involvement spells a change. Their role is necessary to cater to the total development and improvement of the school through collaboration and shared responsibilities.

The researchers then believed that Project UP (Ugnayang Pagbasa) through the collaborative effort of the stakeholders and the teacher will nurture the grit and interest of the learners in Araling Panlipunan. Hence, this study generally aims to improve students' reading comprehension to

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achieve academic performance.

Action Research Questions

This action research will seek to answer the following questions.

- What is the reading level comprehension of Grade 7 learners before and after the administration of Project UP?
- Is there a significant difference in the reading level comprehension of Grade 7 learners between the pre-test and post-test with the implementation of Project UP?
- What intervention could be enhanced based on the results of the study?

Proposed Innovation, Intervention and Strategy

The collaborative effort (Ugnayan) of the stakeholders and experts in teaching reading is the heart of this study. They will be instructed and will undergo thorough briefings on what to do during the process of the program. The researchers will facilitate and monitor the whole process of the activities

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Through this guided procedure the researchers can easily define the level of reading comprehension of G7 learners through constant intervention, assessment, and monitoring.

Action Research Methods

A. Participants

The respondents of the study are the G7 learners who are currently enrolled in the school year 2023 – 2024 at Wawa National High School; they belong to a handful of students who experiences frustration in reading. The basis of the data that falls to frustration reading, are the results of Phil- IRI conducted by English and Filipino teachers. Purposive Sampling will be used in this action proposal.

B. Data Gathering Methods

The researcher will use the PHIL-IRI result to assess learners reading comprehension levels before and after the implementation of PROJECT UP.

The pre-test and post-test will follow to determine the level of reading comprehension with the PROJECT UP. The content of the pre-test and post-test will derive from the given reading materials from ASIAN History with 10 questions.

To collect the needed data for this research, the following steps will be done.

1. Prior to the conduct of the study, the researcher will ask permission from the principal to conduct the study.
2. The researchers will conduct pre-test and post-test using the PHIL-IRI tool to assess the reading comprehension level of the participants.
3. After the pre-test, the stakeholders will start to assist in reading intervention which will take one month.
4. To conclude the research process, the researchers will conduct a post-test, still using the same tool to assess whether the reading comprehension level of the participants improves through the stakeholders' empowerment.
5. The data that will be gathered from the pre-test and post-test will be collated and tabulated.

C. Data Analysis

In order to analyze the data, the researcher will use mean and standard deviation to determine the comprehension level of the learners during the pre-test and post-test. And will use paired sample t-test to determine the significance of the difference between the pre-test and post-test.

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Action Research Work Plan and Timelines

ACTIVITIES	*Month 1	Month 2	Month 3	Month 4	Month 5	Month 6
1. Preparation of research questionnaire						
2. Validating of test questions						
3. Conducting pre-test and post-test						
4. Assessment and evaluation						

**Shade the corresponding month per activity*

Plans for Dissemination and Utilization

DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES	*Month 1	Month 2	Month 3	Month 4	Month 5	Month 6
1. Department meeting						
2. PTA orientation						
3. SLAC						

**Shade the corresponding month per activity*

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Multidisciplinary e-Publication

Volume IV, Issue IV (April 2024) / International Circulation

ISSN (Online) 2799-0842 / ISSN (Print) 2799-130X

Published Online at www.pinagpalapublishing.com

Publisher: Pinagpala Publishing Services

DTI Reg. No. 303443 / TIN 293-150-678 / Bus. Permit No. 8183

National Book Development Board (NBDB) Reg. No. 3269

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DOI 10.5281/zenodo.11081900

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